

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS USING SPSS

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Abstract

This paper presents an integrated statistical analysis of road traffic accidents through a methodologically structured approach using SPSS. The research encompasses three key dimensions of analysis: the effect of wearing seat belts on the number of fatalities, a comparison between current figures and historical averages, and the identification of autocorrelations within time-series data related to traffic accidents. By applying correlation and regression analysis, *t*-tests, and time-series analytical techniques, the study yields significant findings that confirm the interrelation among the examined variables and highlight their influence on safety indicators. The results underscore the importance of quantitative analysis in the effective formulation of evidence-based measures aimed at improving road safety.

Keywords: Analysis, SPSS, statistical methods, traffic accidents, road safety

1. INTRODUCTION

Statistical methods are essential in the scientific investigation of traffic safety, as they enable the identification of underlying patterns in the occurrence of traffic accidents and support the formulation of effective measures for their reduction. Due to their frequency, traffic accidents and conflicts are particularly well suited for statistical analysis (Pešić et al, 2019). The application of statistical techniques provides a detailed understanding of the scope of the problem, the spatial and temporal distribution of accidents, their categorization, as well as the contributing factors that lead to their occurrence (Lord and Mannering, 2010).

In general, statistical methods are classified into two main categories: descriptive statistics, which summarize and present collected data using tables and graphs (e.g., mean,

median, standard deviation, 85th percentile, etc.) and inferential statistics, which are aimed at parameter estimation and the testing of statistical hypotheses (Molugram and Rao, 2017).

2. METHODOLOGY

As part of the statistical examination of road traffic accidents, three research hypotheses were developed and empirically tested to validate specific assumptions:

- A statistically significant relationship exists between front-seat seat belt usage rates in passenger vehicles and the fatality count among front-seat occupants;
- A statistically significant difference will be observed between the 2022 figures for fatalities, seriously injured persons (SIP), and minimally injured persons (MIP), and the corresponding average values recorded over the previous decade;
- The presence of autocorrelation in the residuals derived from regression analysis concerning traffic accidents frequency.

The statistical analysis of road traffic accidents was conducted using the following statistical methods:

- Correlation and regression analysis,
- Mean value testing, and
- Autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation analysis, including forecasting techniques.

The variables used in this study were categorized as dependent and independent. Fatalities among front-seat passengers in passenger vehicles served as dependent variable, while the proportion of seat belt use in the respective seats was the independent variable. The analysis also includes core road safety outcomes – namely accident counts, fatalities and injuries – which were further disaggregated by severity. From another perspective, indirect indicators included seat belt usage, determined through field research on a representative sample.

In the context of correlation and regression analysis, correlation indicates the intensity of the relationship between the variables under study (Amortila et al, 2021). In other words, it shows the extent to which variations in one variable correspond to variations in another. Accordingly, both simple and multiple correlations are considered, and distinctions are made between linear and nonlinear correlations.

The intensity of a linear association between variables is commonly measured using the Pearson correlation coefficient. Its value ranges between -1 , indicating a perfect negative correlation, and 1 , indicating a perfect positive correlation between the studied variables, (Washington, 2010). The coefficient of determination indicates the proportion of variation in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variable. When a dependency is observed between variables, the question arises as to the nature and form of that dependency and whether it can be mathematically modeled (Molugram and Rao, 2017). In such cases, regression analysis is applied, which, like correlation analysis, may take linear or nonlinear forms. Statistical modeling involves fitting a statistical model to data. When a model is used for prediction, it is important that it fits well across the entire range of each variable (Hauer, 2015).

The data used in the analysis concerning the number of traffic accidents and their consequences were obtained from the database of the Macedonian Statistical Office (total number of traffic accidents from 2002 to 2022: 75,810; number of traffic accidents in 2022:

3,951; total number of fatalities from 2002 to 2022: 3,110; total number of persons with serious injuries (SIP) from 2002 to 2022: 18,113; and total number of persons with minor injuries (MIP): 103,388). Due to the unavailability of domestic data on indirect indicators related to seatbelt usage, data from the Serbian road safety database (number of front-seat fatalities from 2016 to 2022 and the percentage of front-seat seat belt usage for front seats during the same period) were used to validate the specified assumption.

The statistical analysis employed the SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software, which enables the application of various statistical techniques for data processing (Landau and Everitt, 2004).

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the collective risk analysis of road traffic accidents on express roads, by road section and by year, are presented in Table 5.

2.1. Correlation and Regression Analysis

The outcomes of the linear correlation analysis between the number of fatalities among front-seat occupants in passenger vehicles and the front-seat belt usage are presented in the following tables.

Table 1. Arithmetic Mean and Standard Deviation of the Variables

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Fatalities in Front Seats	46.71	12.606	7
Percentage of Seat Belt Usage in Front Seats	81.7286	4.24959	7

Table 2. Pearson Correlation Coefficient

		Fatalities in Front Seats	Front-seat belt usage
Fatalities in Front Seats	Pearson Correlation	1	-.873)*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.010
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	953.429	-280.743)
	Covariance	158.905	-46.790)
	N	7	7
Front-seat belt usage	Pearson Correlation	-.873)*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	-280.743)	108.354
	Covariance	-46.790)	18.059
	N	7	7
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

The results demonstrate that the Pearson correlation coefficient is -0.873 ($r < -0.75$), indicating a strong negative linear correlation between front-seat belt usage and the number of fatalities in front seats of passenger vehicles.

The significance level is 0.01 ($p < 0.05$), confirming a statistically significant linear association.

The outcomes of the regression analysis concerning the number of fatalities in front seats of passenger vehicles and the percentage of seat belt usage in those seats are presented below.

Table 3. Model Summary Data^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.873a	.763	.716	6.724

a. Predictors: (Constant), Percentage of Seat Belt Usage in Front Seats

b. Dependent Variable: Fatalities in Front Seats

Table 4. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	727.397	1	727.397	16.091	.010b
	Residual	226.032	5	45.206		
	Total	953.429	6			

a. Dependent Variable: Fatalities in Front Seats

b. Predictors: (Constant), Percentage of Seat Belt Usage in Front Seats

Table 5. Model Parameters^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	258.471	52.851		4.891	.005	122.613	394.329
	Percentage of Seat Belt Usage in Front Seats	-2.591	.646	-.873)	-4.011)	.010	-4.251)	-.931)

Dependent Variable: Fatalities in Front Seats

The coefficient of determination is 0.763 ; however, given the small sample size, the adjusted coefficient of determination is more appropriate. Its value is 0.716 , indicating that 71.6% of the variance in the number of front-seat fatalities in passenger vehicles is explained by front-seat seat belt usage. The results of the Student's t -test and the associated p -values ($p < 0.05$), with a confidence level of 95% , support the conclusion that the regression model is statistically valid. These findings suggest that the front-seat belt usage has a substantial effect on reducing the fatalities among front-seat occupants.

2.2. Mean Value Testing

To examine the outcomes resulting from traffic accidents over the past ten years, the study tested the recorded number of fatalities, seriously injured persons (SIP), and minimally injured persons (MIP) in 2022. The results of the T-test focused on traffic-related fatalities recorded in 2022 are presented below.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics on the Recorded Fatalities in the Past 10 Years

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Number of Fatalities	10	142.60	24.677	7.803

Table 7. T-Test Results for the Recorded Fatalities in 2022

		Test Value = 124					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Interval Difference Lower	Confidence of the Difference Upper
Number of Fatalities		2.384	9	.041	18.600	.95	36.25

According to the T-test, with 9 degrees of freedom and a significance threshold of $p = 0.05$, the calculated t-value is 2.384, and the p-value is 0.041. This indicates that the 2022 fatality figures differ significantly from the average over the previous ten years. Accordingly, the findings suggest that, with respect to fatalities, the situation in 2022 is more favorable compared to the past decade.

The results of the T-test applied to evaluate the incidence of serious injuries caused by road traffic accidents in 2022 are presented below.

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics on the Number of Seriously Injured Persons in the Past 10 Years

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Number of SIP	10	837.00	44.875	14.191

Table 9. Test Results for the Number of Seriously Injured Persons in 2022

	Test Value = 820					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Number of SIP	1.198	9	.262	17.000	-15.10)	49.10

According to the results of the T-test, with 9 degrees of freedom and a significance threshold of 0.05, a t-value of 1.198 was obtained, along with a significance level of 0.262. From a statistical point of view, the 2022 figures on serious injuries do not exhibit significant deviations from the average number of seriously injured persons over the past ten years. This leads to the conclusion that the situation in 2022 concerning seriously injured persons in traffic accidents is less favorable compared to the previous 10-year period.

The results of the T-test used to evaluate incidence of individuals with minor injuries resulting from traffic accidents in 2022 are presented below.

Table 10. Descriptive Statistics on the Number of Minimally Injured Persons in the Past 10 Years

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Number of MIP	10	5102.20	447.030	141.363

Table 11. T – Test Results for the Number of Minimally Injured Persons in 2022

	Test Value = 4500					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Number of MIP	4.260	9	.002	602.200	282.41	921.99

According to the results of this test and the significance threshold, a t-value of 4.260 was obtained, along with a significance level of 0.002. From a statistical standpoint, it can be determined that that the 2022 figures concerning individuals with minor injuries (MIP) differ significantly from the average number recorded over the past ten years. Furthermore, it can be concluded that the situation in 2022 concerning individuals with minor injuries resulting from traffic accidents is more favorable compared to the previous ten-year period.

2.3. Autocorrelation Analysis and Forecasting

In the autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation analysis, the assumption of independence among residual values in the time series data was tested. For this analysis and for forecasting the total count of traffic accidents, data from 2002 to 2022 were used. The results of the autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation analysis are presented below.

Fig. 1. (a) Autocorrelation plot; (b) Partial autocorrelation plot.

According to the results obtained from the autocorrelation analysis, the significance level for all periods ranges from 0 to 0.012, indicating that the data is statistically significant across all periods. Therefore, it can be inferred that the traffic accident data for the observed period are suitable for predictive modeling. From the autocorrelation plot and partial autocorrelation plot, it is evident that the autocorrelation values indicate the presence of a trend in the observed values.

The Durbin–Watson d -test is commonly used to identify autocorrelation in the residuals of a regression model, (Gošić et al, 2022). The result of the Durbin–Watson test is $d = 0.257$. Since $d < 2$, it can be concluded that positive autocorrelation is present.

To determine the most suitable forecasting model based on the Exponential Smoothing method, a summary of results was prepared, including RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error), MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error), MAE (Mean Absolute Error), and R^2 (Coefficient of Determination), as shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Model Selection Data for Forecasting

Exponential smoothing type	model	RMSE	MAPE	MAE	R2
Holt		360.257	7.713	277.104	0.825
Brown		367.833	8.979	310.882	0.808
Damped Trend		356.182	7.600	269.143	0.838

The model with the lowest values for RMSE, MARE, and MAE, and the highest value for R^2 , is considered the most suitable for predicting traffic accident counts. Based on the comparison of values presented in Table 12, it can be concluded that the most appropriate forecasting model using the Exponential Smoothing method is the Damped Trend model.

The results of the forecasted traffic accident counts using the Exponential Smoothing method with the Damped Trend model are presented in the following tables and figures.

Table 13. Forecast of the Traffic Accident Counts through 2030

Model		2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
No_SN- Model_1	Forecast	3979	4004	4026	4046	4064	4079	4093	4106
	UCL	4727	5171	5582	5978	6365	6745	7117	7482
	LCL	3231	2837	2471	2114	1762	1414	1070	730

Fig. 2. Forecast of the Number of Traffic Accidents through 2030

Based on the forecasting results, a slight upward trend in traffic accident counts is expected over the next eight years. Specifically, the number of traffic accidents in 2030 is projected to reach 4,106. Compared to the recorded number of traffic accidents in 2022, this represents an increase of 155 accidents, or approximately 3.92%.

3. CONCLUSION

This study enabled a comprehensive analysis of traffic safety through the application of correlation and regression analysis, mean value testing, and autocorrelation analysis. The results confirmed a significant relationship between seat belt usage and the number of fatalities among front-seat occupants in passenger vehicles, as well as a statistically significant variation of fatalities and minimally injured persons in 2022 compared to the average over the past ten years. The only exception was the number of seriously injured persons, for which no statistically significant difference was observed. In addition, autocorrelation of the regression residuals for traffic accident counts was identified, validating the data for future forecasting.

Regular statistical analysis of traffic safety data is essential, as it enables the identification of underlying patterns in traffic accidents and provides a scientific basis for defining effective measures and interventions aimed at reducing them. The SPSS software package proved to be a suitable and effective tool for conducting such complex statistical analyses.

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